

Geomagnetic Ap Index (1954-2024) as a Leading Indicator of the Fed Rate (1955 - 2025) ($R^2=0.9733$): The Role of UV Index, Serotonin-Melatonin Balance, and Collective Optimism-Pessimism

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Abstract

The report uses a methodological approach developed by W. S. Jevons and A. L. Chizhevsky. Solar cycle years were numbered according to the order established in solar astrophysics, grouped, and compared with the arithmetic mean values of the geomagnetic index Ap and the effective US federal funds rate with a lag of 1 year.

The results showed that the Fed's interest rate with a 1-year lag is minimal in years of extreme values (maximums and minimums) of the geomagnetic index Ap.

During periods of maximum values of the geomagnetic index Ap, suppressed melatonin synthesis and the accompanying serotonin deficiency lead to increased pessimism. During periods of minimum values of the geomagnetic index Ap, which are characterized by a low ultraviolet index, insufficient serotonin synthesis and increased pessimism are observed. In both cases, collective pessimism triggers a slowdown in business activity, forcing the Federal Reserve to lower interest rates to stimulate the economy.

The coefficient of determination in the diagram average geomagnetic activity coefficient Ap - average Fed interest rate with a one-year lag is 0.9733. This means that the current year's Ap coefficient can be used to determine the forecast value of the Fed interest rate next year. The forecast value of the Fed interest rate for 2026 is 3.75%, and for 2027, 3.3%.

The study also found a strong correlation between the geomagnetic Ap index and annual US GDP growth rates over the period 1954–2025. Annual US GDP growth rates decline significantly at extremes of the geomagnetic Ap index,

prompting the Federal Reserve to lower the Fed rate with a lag of approximately one year. The projected annual US GDP growth rate for 2026 is 2.6%.

Keywords:

Fed interest rates, solar cycles, Wolf numbers, geomagnetic index A_p , melatonin, serotonin, behavioral economics, economic cycles, forecasting

In his article “Solar-Commercial Cycles,” W. S. Jevons plotted solar activity cycles (Wolf number cycles) and corn price cycles in Delhi over the period 1760–1810 [1, P.227], that is, he compared solar and economic activity.

Chizhevsky A. L. in his monograph “The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun” in Chapter 4 “The Sun and Epidemics” in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that depicts **the average solar activity cycle** over a hundred years (the cycle of Wolf numbers) and the average cases of cholera in Russia for the years of the solar cycle for the period 1823-1923 [2, p. 201].

That is, A. L. Chizhevsky actively used the method of superposition of epochs (a statistical method for studying cyclic processes) in his fundamental works on heliobiology and heliosociology. This method is used in this preprint.

The annual mean Wolf numbers, the main indicator of solar activity (SA), were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [3]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The ordinal numbers of years in column 3 of Table 1 are determined as follows. The first year in a SA cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, that is, the increase in the Wolf number, which is presented in column 2. Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the SA minimum. Years of Wolf number minimums in Table 1 are highlighted in blue. Years of maximums are highlighted in red.

Annual monthly average values of the geomagnetic index A_p for the period 1955–2025 were obtained from the Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences website [4] and are presented in column 4 of Table 1.

The Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis website provides statistical data on annual effective federal funds rates for the period 1955–2025 [5]. These are presented in column 5 of Table 1.

Table 1. Average annual Wolf numbers, solar cycle ordinal numbers, geomagnetic activity index A_p (1954-2025) and effective federal funds rates, 1955–2025

The years	Wolf numbers, 1954 - 2025	The serial number of the year in the cycle of solar activity	Geomagnetic activity index A_p .	Fed rate, %, 1955-2025	Fed rate with a lag of 1 year, %
1	2	3	4	5	6
1954	6.6	10	11.0	No data	1.785
1955	54.2	1	11.3	1.785	2.728333333
1956	200.7	2	18.1	2.728333333	3.105
1957	269.3	3	20.2	3.105	1.5725
1958	261.7	4	19.3	1.5725	3.305
1959	225.1	5	21.3	3.305	3.215833333
1960	159	6	23.7	3.215833333	1.955
1961	76.4	7	14.4	1.955	2.708333333
1962	53.4	8	12.3	2.708333333	3.178333333
1963	39.9	9	12.6	3.178333333	3.496666667
1964	15	10	9.9	3.496666667	4.0725
1965	22	1	7.8	4.0725	5.110833333
1966	66.8	2	10.3	5.110833333	4.22
1967	132.9	3	12	4.22	5.656666667
1968	150	4	13.5	5.656666667	8.204166667
1969	149.4	5	11.4	8.204166667	7.180833333
1970	148	6	11.9	7.180833333	4.660833333

1971	94.4	7	11.3	4.660833333	4.430833333
1972	97.6	8	12.6	4.430833333	8.7275
1973	54.1	9	17.1	8.7275	10.5025
1974	49.2	10	19.6	10.5025	5.824166667
1975	22.5	11	13.9	5.824166667	5.045
1976	18.4	12	12.9	5.045	5.5375
1977	39.3	1	11.9	5.5375	7.930833333
1978	131	2	16.9	7.930833333	11.19416667
1979	220.1	3	14.5	11.19416667	13.35583333
1980	218.9	4	11.1	13.35583333	16.37833333
1981	198.9	5	16.3	16.37833333	12.25833333
1982	162.4	6	22.5	12.25833333	9.086666667
1983	91	7	18.6	9.086666667	10.225
1984	60.5	8	18.8	10.225	8.100833333
1985	20.6	9	13.7	8.100833333	6.805
1986	14.8	10	12.6	6.805	6.6575
1987	33.9	1	10.9	6.6575	7.568333333
1988	123	2	12 ,7	7.568333333	9.216666667
1989	211.1	3	19.4	9.216666667	8.099166667
1990	19 1.8	4	16.3	8.099166667	5.6875
1991	203.3	5	23.4	5.6875	3.521666667
1992	133	6	16.6	3.521666667	3.0225
1993	76.1	7	15	3.0225	4.201666667
1994	44.9	8	18.2	4.201666667	5.836666667
1995	25.1	9	12.7	5.836666667	5.298333333
1996	11.6	10	9.3	5.298333333	5.46
1997	28.9	1	8.4	5.46	5.353333333
1998	88.3	2	12	5.353333333	4.97
1999	136.3	3	12.5	4.97	6.235833333

2000	173.9	4	15	6.235833333	3.8875
2001	170.4	5	12.9	3.8875	1.666666667
2002	163.6	6	13.1	1.666666667	1.1275
2003	99.3	7	21.7	1.1275	1.349166667
2004	65.3	8	13.4	1.349166667	3.213333333
2005	45.8	9	13.5	3.213333333	4.964166667
2006	24.7	10	8.4	4.964166667	5.019166667
2007	12.6	11	7.5	5.019166667	1.9275
2008	4.2	12	6.9	1.9275	0.16
2009	4.8	1	3.9	0.16	0.175
2010	24.9	2	6	0.175	0.101666667
2011	80.8	3	7.5	0.101666667	0.14
2012	84.5	4	9.1	0.14	0.1075
2013	94	5	7.6	0.1075	0.089166667
2014	113.3	6	7.7	0.089166667	0.1325
2015	69.8	7	12.2	0.1325	0.395
2016	39.8	8	10.5	0.395	1.001666667
2017	21.7	9	10.3	1.001666667	1.831666667
2018	7	10	6.9	1.831666667	2.158333333
2019	3.6	11	6.1	2.158333333	0.375833333
2020	8.8	1	5.3	0.375833333	0.08
2021	29.6	2	7.2	0.08	1.68
2022	83.2	3	10.1	1.68	5.02
2023	125.5	4	10.9	5.02	5.14
2024	154.7	5	11.7	5.14	4.21
2025	123.2	6	15.5	4.21	
2026		7			
2027		8			

The statistical data in Table 1 were then grouped by the ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles. Column 2 of Table 2 shows the number of such years for the period 1954–2024.

Table 2. Grouping of data from Table 1 by ordinal numbers of years in solar activity cycles

1. The serial number of the year in the cycle of solar activity.	2. The number of such years for the period 1954-2024	Arithmetic mean:		5. Ratio to the previous year's rate
		3. geomagnetic activity index Ap, 1954-2024	4. Fed rate with a lag of 1 year, %, 1955-2025	
1	7	8.5	4.135	1.452
2	7	11.9	4.927	1.191
3	7	13.7	5.726	1.162
4	7	13.6	6.101	1.066
5	7	14.9	4.592	0.753
6	7	15.9	3.331	0.725
7	6	15.5	3.885	1.166
8	6	14.3	5.010	1.290
9	6	13.3	5.483	1.094
10	6	11.1	4.425	0.807
11	3	9.2	2.449	0.554

12	2	9.9	2.849	1.163
Total:	71			

The following diagram (see Fig. 1) constructed based on the data in rows 1–12 and columns 1, 3, and 4 of Table 2.

Fig. 1. Average geomagnetic index Ap (1954-2024) and Fed rates with a lag of 1 year (1955-2025) by years of the average (12 years) solar cycle (epoch overlap method), 71 years of observations

P.E. Grigoriev in his article identified a tendency for the mental state of subjects to deteriorate in the vicinity of dates of geomagnetic disturbances and geomagnetic calms [7, p. 67], that is, magnetic extremes.

“It is now firmly established that exposure to magnetic fields results in a reduction in the synthesis and content of melatonin in the pineal gland, as well as a

reduction in the level of melatonin in the blood in several species... including humans," notes Russell Reiter in his work. [8, p.171].

A **decrease in melatonin** levels due to an increase in the Ap index (see point 6 in Fig. 1) inevitably leads to a disruption in serotonin metabolism, as these two substances are linked by a single biochemical pathway (tryptophan → serotonin → melatonin). A failure in the final link (melatonin) leads to depletion of serotonin stores via a feedback loop.

A decrease in melatonin levels at night due to a high Ap index disrupts the brain's rhythmic functioning. This leads to neurons failing to maintain adequate serotonin levels during the day, leading to emotional decline (**pessimism**).

According to Reuters, melatonin is a powerful antioxidant. When its levels drop due to magnetic activity, the brain experiences oxidative stress. The body uses serotonin as a secondary resource to try to stabilize neurochemical levels, leading to its deficiency ("burnout").

Ultimately, an increase in the geomagnetic index Ap leads to melatonin suppression, a systemic **serotonin deficiency**, and increased anxiety and pessimism in society. This is followed by a deterioration in macroeconomic indicators, which prompts the Federal Reserve to lower the interest rate (see points 6 and in Figure 1).

Points 1 and 11 in Fig. 1 are characterized by **minimum** values of the geomagnetic index Ap and minimum SA. This corresponds to the **minimum** value of the ultraviolet index (**UV index**) in the cycle. A low UV index leads to **decreased serotonin levels**.

Low serotonin is a classic trigger for depression, social apathy, and pessimism. This is the bearish phase, when people are afraid to take risks and save. Collective pessimism leads to an economic slowdown and a decline in demand. To save the situation, the Fed lowers interest rates, stimulating the apathetic market with cheap money.

A 1-year lag is the total time required for an impulse to travel along the chain: Cosmic Factor→Mass Psychophysiology→Economic Behavior→Statistical Report→Federal Reserve Decision."

The diagram in Fig. 2 is constructed based on the data from rows 1–12 and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2. From a mathematical perspective, the high value of the coefficient of determination in this diagram (0.9733) makes the model very robust for forecasting.

For example, the geomagnetic index Ap for 2025 is equal to 15.5 and on the diagram in Fig. 2 it corresponds to the forecast value of the Fed rate for 2026, equal to 3.75%.

The geomagnetic index forecast for 2026 can be determined based on a diagram copied from the NASA website [9] (see the green curve in Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Average Fed rates with a 1-year lag as a function of average values of the geomagnetic index Ap, 12 years, average solar cycle for 1954–2024, 71 years of observations

Fig. 3. Forecast of the geomagnetic index Ap.

The diagram in Fig. 3 allows us to determine the forecast value of the geomagnetic activity index Ap for 2026 (see the green curve). A visual assessment yields a value of 16. Therefore, the forecast value of the Fed interest rate for 2027 is 3.30%.

Figure 4 shows a diagram that shows a strong relationship between the average geomagnetic index Ap and annual growth rates of US GDP for the period 1954-2025 for years 1-6 ($R^2=0.78$, $R=0.88$), and in Figure 5 for years 7-12 of the SA cycles ($R^2=0.82$, $R=0.91$). Data on US GDP were taken from the website of the Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis [6]. These results were obtained using the superposition of epochs method and represent 72 years of observations.

The charts show that the annual growth rate of US GDP significantly decreases in the region of extremes (maximums and minimums) of the geomagnetic index Ap, which forces the US Federal Reserve to cut the rate with a lag of 1 year.

The year 2026 is the 7th year of the current 25th SA cycle with a forecast value of the geomagnetic index Ap equal to 16.0 (see Fig. 3), which in the diagram in Fig. 5 corresponds to a forecast value of the US GDP index equal to 2.6%.

Fig. 4. Average annual growth rates of US GDP as a function of the average geomagnetic index Ap, years 1–6 of the SA cycles for 1954–2025, 42 years of observations, superposition method

Fig. 5. Average annual growth rates of US GDP as a function of the average geomagnetic index Ap, 7-12 years of the SA cycles for 1954-2025, 30 years of observations, superposition method

Conclusions of the study

1. Identification of a fundamental connection: The study confirms A. L. Chizhevsky's hypothesis about the influence of cosmic factors on socio-economic processes. A close link has been established between geomagnetic activity (the index Ap) and the monetary policy of the US Federal Reserve.

2. Biophysical mechanism: The relationship is based on the psychophysiological reaction of the masses to geomagnetic activity extremes. Hormonal imbalances (serotonin deficiency) during periods of abnormal index Ap provokes collective pessimism, leading to a slowdown in business activity.

3. Monetary cycle pattern: The Federal Reserve rate acts as a reactive instrument. The regulator is forced to lower interest rates with a one-year lag in response to the economic downturn caused by the decline in public "mental tone" during periods of geomagnetic activity extremes.

4. High predictive accuracy: The coefficient of determination $R^2=0.9733$ mathematically proves that the overlapping era model eliminates market noise and allows the current year's index A_p to be used as a reliable leading indicator for interest rate forecasts.

5. Practical forecast:

– According to the model, the Fed is expected to gradually cut the interest rate to 3.75% in 2026 and to 3.3% in 2027.

— annual growth of US GDP in 2026 will be 2.6%.

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